

Large-scale landslides hiding the geothermal potential of San Agustín del Maíz geothermal field, México

Jorge Alejandro Guevara-Alday^{1,4}, Víctor Hugo Garduño-Monroy^{2,4} †, Emanuel Olvera-García^{3,4}, Sergio Manuel Nájera-Blas⁴, Mikhail Ostrooumov², Alain Tremblay¹

1. University of Quebec in Montreal, Department of Earth and Atmospheric sciences H2X3Y7, Montreal, Canada
2. Michoacán University of “San Nicolas de Hidalgo”, Research Institute in Earth Sciences, 58060 Morelia, Mexico
3. University of Bari “Aldo Moro”, Department of Earth and Geoenvironmental, 70125 Bari, Italy
4. Mexican Center of Innovation in Geothermal Energy (CeMIEGeo), 22860 Ensenada, México
Correspondent author email: aguevaraalday@gmail.com

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Abstract

Large-scale landslides are usually linked to fault ruptures in active tectonic settings, most of the time in step slopes landscapes. San Agustín del Maíz geothermal field is located within the Cuitzeo basin at the central sector of the Trans-Mexican Volcanic Belt (TMVB), where thanks to remote sensing and fieldwork were recognized five hills formed by landslides covering part of the geothermal upwelling, these landslides are made up by broken fragments of pyroclastic deposits and andesites from the surroundings which are hydrothermal altered and contain veins made of calcite, quartz, chlorite and opal crystals.

1. Introduction

Commonly large-scale landslides are triggered by a wide number of factors, including anomalous rainfalls, rapid snow melts, volcanic eruption (Cruden and Varnes 1996). Although, within continental volcanic belts characterized by active tectonics, landslides are frequently triggered by earthquakes or swarms of them (Evans et al. 1987).

The study area is located in the Cuitzeo tectonic basin, in the central part of the TMVB (Demant 1978). This volcanic province dates back to the middle to late Miocene (Ferrari et. al. 1999) and derives from the subduction of the Cocos plate under the North American plate along the Pacific trencher (Demant 1978) (Fig. 1a). The evidences of geothermal activity located on the south shore of Cuitzeo Lake are: thermal pools, mug volcanos, fossil and current sinter deposits which follow NE – SW and NW – SE trends and reach temperatures up to 94 °C.

2. Methods and techniques

A morpho-structural analysis was performed using 5 m resolution LIDAR (Laser Imagen Detection and Ranging) and complemented by using orthophotos and aerial photographs products of National Institute of Statistic and Geographic (INEGI by its acronym in Spanish). Then were carried out structural stations along fault traces and dots around the allochthonous bodies by classic field mapping and stratigraphic sections.

Fig. 1 a) Geodynamic context of the Tran-Mexican Volcanic Belt (TMVB) and the Michoacan-Guanajuato Volcanic Field (MGVF); b) geological map illustrating the geological evolution since Mesozoic until today; c) synthetic geological map of the interest area, showing the distribution of fossil and current thermal manifestations in red dots and the depletion zones identified along San Agustín del Maíz fault scarp. Mo: Morelia; SMOVA: Sierra Madre Oriental Volcanic Belt.

3. Results

The geological sequence of the study area consist of: a well fractured andesite sequence named Mil Cumbres Andesite (MC) of 21.5 Ma at the bottom, followed by a ~140 m of pyroclastic deposits package named Cuitzeo Pyroclastic Sequence (CPS) expose mainly along the ENE – WSW fault scarp (Fig 1c) and with evidences of hydrothermal alteration in the middle and at the bottom of the slope, overlaying this sequences there are the first evidences of monogenic activity from Tarímbaro sequences of <18.6 Ma, which is part of the Michoacán Guanajuato Volcanic Field (MGVF). The entire sequence is tilting 32° southward due to ENE – WSW striking listric faults, dipping toward NW (Fig 2h). The top of the lithological sequence is crowded by Lacustrine Deposits of Cuitzeo Lake (LD), filling the tectonic basin (Fig 2a). Particularly

important are some outcrops at El Caido (the biggest landslide) that exhibit evidences of fossil hydrothermal activity, filling with calcite \pm chloride \pm quartz and structural attitude unlike (Fig. 2h) of the units located south along the fault scarp, also important are some small outcrops with stockwork structures (Fig. 2i).

Fig. 2 a) Stratigraphic column type along San Agustín del Maíz fault scarp. b) San Agustín del Maíz fault plane where was identified a tectonic breccia enlarged in c) and slickensides in secondary mineralization in d); e) Damage zone next to SJT that exhibit a uncountable number of fault planes which are strike slip and oblique faults striking N – S often filling by Cal \pm Cl and normal fault striking NE – SW; h) internal architecture of El Caido with some erosional contacts on top; i) stockwork structure filling with Cal \pm Cl veins.

After the analysis of fault populations were recognize two different fault sets: 1) Normal faults striking ENE – WSW and dipping NW with lateral component (both right and left) (Fig. 1c); controlling the morphology of the region and acting as rise pathways for hydrothermal fluids in San Agustín geothermal field. 2) Right lateral strike slip and oblique faults striking from NNW – SSE to NNE-SSW (Fig. 1c) were defined as a fault zone located between San Agustín del Maíz (SAM) and San Juan Tarameo (SJT). Based on its position between two normal faults it is considered as a transfer zone between San Agustín del Maíz and Chehuayo faults.

4. Discussion

Although depletion zones are not present across the area in the most cases probably because weathering, some evidences over the principal slope NE – SW trend such as concave crowns forward the slipping direction (Fig. 1c)

and the internal structure of every large-scale landslide on Cuitzeo basing like random tilting (Fig. 3a, 3e), classified them how rotational landslides. With respect of their role as caprock of a geothermal field, it is well known slip surface could be affected by weathering developing a clay layer that acts how an impermeable surface allowing a reactivation of the body (Rotaru et. al. 2007). Keeping this in mind, clay layers may also act how a fluid boundary in both senses downward and upward, cutting off the rise of hydrothermal fluids through it.

5. Conclusions

The Miocenic tectonic activity has performed an important role since the first stages of TMVB up to date controlling the volcanic activity, morphology and even extension thought tectonics basins like Cuitzeo Lake. Paleo seismic and recent records of this constant tectonic activity proved not only its potential seismic hazard to cities but its high potentially as trigger of large-scale landslides such as they founded on Cuitzeo basin.

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